

Geographical Indications (GI) in India: A State-Wise Comparative Study

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Abstract: *The Geographical Indications (GI) are a form of intellectual property that recognize products as originating from a specific geographical location. India has registered a wide range of GI products, including agricultural goods, handicrafts, manufactured items, and natural products. However, the distribution of GI tags across Indian states has been uneven, with some states leading in registrations while others remain underrepresented. This study aims to conduct a comparative analysis of the state-wise distribution of GI tags in India. By categorizing and comparing GI registrations, the study highlights gaps, and suggests to encourage all stake holders. The findings aim to support to the related people and local communities in leveraging GI protection for inclusive economic growth and cultural preservation.*

Keywords: Geographical Indications (GI), GI Tags in India, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Regional Identity, Traditional Knowledge, Cultural Heritage Protection

1 Introduction

India is a land of immense cultural, agricultural, and artisanal diversity, reflected vividly through its wide array of region-specific products. From the aromatic Basmati rice of the north to the intricate Kancheepuram silk sarees of the south, each region of India boasts unique goods that are deeply rooted in tradition, geography, and community identity. These goods are more than just goods; they are symbols of pride, history, and local identity. These products, often crafted using traditional knowledge and natural resources specific to their region, are legally protected under the framework of Geographical Indications (GI).

Over the years, hundreds of products from different states have been registered under GI, spanning categories such as agricultural products, handicrafts, manufactured goods, and natural products. However, the distribution of these GI tags is not uniform across Indian states. Some states have taken proactive steps to identify and register local products, while others lag behind due to lack of awareness, institutional support, or policy initiative.

This study aims to undertake a comparative analysis of the state-wise distribution of GI tags in India, exploring the reasons behind the disparity and the types of products registered. It also seeks to identify best practices adopted by leading states and recommend strategies to ensure more balanced and inclusive GI registration across the country.

2 Geographical Indications (GI)

The term "geographic indications of goods" describes a type of economic property that indicates a country or a region within it is the country or place of origin of a certain product. Such a name typically conveys a sense of quality and originality, primarily because it originated in that particular region, country, or geographic place. Articles 1(2) and 10 of the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property acknowledge geographic indicators as a component of IPRs (About us, n.d.). The Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) Agreement, which was one of the agreements that concluded the Uruguay Round of GATT negotiations, also covers them in Articles 22 to 24 (Overview: the TRIPS Agreement, n.d.; InsightsIAS, October 23, 2023). In India, GI tags are governed by the Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act, 1999, which came into effect in 2003 (Geographical Indications, n.d.).

2.1 Purpose of GI Tags:

- Preserve cultural heritage and biodiversity
- Prevent unauthorized use or imitation
- Promote rural and artisanal economies
- Protect the unique identity of traditional products

2.2 Categories of GI-Tagged Products in India:

- Agricultural Products – Basmati Rice, Alphonso Mango, Bhut Jolokia etc.
- Handicrafts – Pashmina Shawls, Madhubani Paintings, Channapatna Toys and so on.
- Manufactured Goods – Banarasi Sarees, Blue Pottery of Jaipur etc.
- Natural Goods – Kashmiri Saffron, Lakadong Turmeric and so on.

2.3 Benefits of GI Tags (<https://ariyalur.nic.in>):

- Boosts employment and rural development
- Encourages traditional knowledge preservation
- Ensures legal protection for producers
- Increases market value and access to global markets

3 Objectives

The main objectives of this study are as follows:

- To analyze the distribution of GI tags across different states in India.
- To categorize GI tags based on product types (Agricultural, Handicraft, Manufactured, and Natural Goods).
- To identify gaps and challenges in the equitable distribution of GI registrations across India.
- To recommend strategies for improving the state-wise distribution and effectiveness of GI registrations.

4 Methodology

The study has followed for capturing data through online survey which includes the websites, reports, journals, web pages, blogs etc. Numerical data are available in the portal of Office of the Controller General of Patents, Design & Trade Marks, Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade, Ministry of Commerce & Industry, Government of India. This website includes all GI status i.e. refused, registered, withdrawn, abandoned and pending applications in this regard. All the data have been collected upto the period of July 26, 2024. A total of 605 data have been collected which include GI applications registered upto this period Rudrajyoti, M. (n.d.). The study has considered the goods registered by the States/UTs individually or jointly. Goods details have been collected from the website of Geographical Indications Registry (<https://search.ipindia.gov.in/GIRPublic/>). This website includes all GI status i.e. refused, registered, withdrawn, abandoned and pending applications in this regard.

5 Review of Literature

The WTO (1994) defines GIs under Article 22.1 of TRIPS as: “*Indications which identify a good as originating in the territory of a Member... where a given quality, reputation or other characteristic of the good is essentially attributable to its geographical origin.*” Several scholars (Rangnekar, 2004; Giovannucci et al., 2009) stress that GIs encompass not only geographical origin but also embedded traditional knowledge, production methods, and cultural identity.

The effectiveness of GIs is largely dependent on the legal features of GIs and the various ideas of GIs with various areas of TRIPS provisions on GIs and compares these provisions with the comparable provisions of the Indian GI Act (Srivastava, 2003; Das, 2006). Legal scholars such as Gangjee (2007) explore the interface between trademark law and GIs, highlighting the legal pluralism in GI protection across countries. GIs have been promoted as tools for rural development and economic empowerment.

According to Barham (2003) and Belletti & Marescotti (2011), GI products often command a price premium, ensure product differentiation, and support sustainable local economies. Some studies (Sylvander, 2004; Bramley et al., 2009) argue that GIs enhance international trade by serving as signals of quality. However, the benefits are unevenly distributed due to market access barriers and differing legal regimes. GI protection is often seen as a way to preserve cultural heritage and collective identity (Bowen, 2010). It safeguards traditional practices and links them to specific landscapes and communities.

Numerous geographic indicators have been examined in relation to rural development and the bolstering of India's economy (Vats, 2016). Numerous studies on GIs have been discussed in the fields of food (Seal & Piramanayagam, 2018; Marie-Vivien, 2016; Chavan, 2022), Indian agriculture (Chaudhary, Yadav & Kumar, 2017), and horticulture (Kishore, 2019). The history and development of GIs in India (Maurya, 2022) and the different difficulties faced in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic (Mishra, 2022) are two further studies that are important for the efficacy of GIs. This study assesses GIs' current efficacy in India.

Developing countries have pushed for expanded GI protections to promote their indigenous products. Recent literature (Belletti et al., 2017) explores the role of GIs in promoting environmentally sustainable practices, particularly in agriculture. Global markets face issues of counterfeiting and misappropriation of GI tags. Enforcement mechanisms remain weak in many jurisdictions (WIPO, 2020).

6. Data Collections and Analysis

6.1 State wise distribution of GIs registration

A total of 588 goods (As per Sec 2 (f) of GI Act 1999) have been registered by different States and UTs separately in the Patent Office in India up to July 26, 2024. The following table shows the distribution of the goods registration by the States during this period.

Table 1: Statement showing state wise distribution of GI Tags

S.N.	States/UTs	Total	%
1	Andhra Pradesh	19	3.23
2	Arunachal Pradesh	19	3.23
3	Assam	31	5.27
4	Bihar	16	2.72
5	Chhattisgarh	7	1.19
6	Goa	10	1.70
7	Gujarat	27	4.59
8	Himachal Pradesh	10	1.70
9	Jammu & Kashmir	16	2.72
10	Jharkhand	1	0.17
11	Karnataka	44	7.48
12	Kerala	35	5.95
13	Ladakh (UT)	4	0.68
14	Madhya Pradesh	21	3.57
15	Maharashtra	49	8.33
16	Manipur	6	1.02
17	Meghalaya	6	1.02
18	Mizoram	7	1.19
19	Nagaland	4	0.68
20	Odisha	26	4.42
21	Pondicherry	2	0.34
22	Rajasthan	20	3.40
23	Sikkim	1	0.17
24	Tamil Nadu	59	10.03
25	Telangana	17	2.89
26	Tripura	4	0.68
27	Uttar Pradesh	74	12.59
28	Uttarakhand	26	4.42
29	West Bengal	27	4.59
Total		588	100.00

Chart 1: State wise distribution of GI registrations

Results: The above table and chart show that highest number of GI tags i.e. 74 (12.59% of total GI application by each State i.e. 588) are found in Uttar Pradesh and then Tamil Nadu shows 59 Tags (10.03%). Third and fourth positions hold Maharashtra (49 GI Tags i.e. 8.33%) and Karnataka (44 GI Tags i.e. 7.48%) respectively. A total number of 27 GI Tags (4.59%) are found in West Bengal.

6.2 Joint GI Tags holders

Although GI tags safeguard goods associated with a particular region, the same GI product is frequently produced by numerous small manufacturers or artisan groups in that area. To ensure that everyone in that area benefits, the GI is owned by a number of stakeholders rather than a single state or UT. Therefore, some goods have been registered of GI Tags by two or more states and/or Union

Territories (UTs). GI law of India encourages joint ownership to represent all legitimate producers fairly.

Table 2: Statement showing GI Tags registered by more than one state

S.N.	States/UTs	Agricultural	Handicraft	Total
1	Arunachal Pradesh and Assam	1	-	1
2	Kerala, Karnataka & Tamil Nadu	1	-	1
3	Maharashtra & Madhya Pradesh	1	-	1
4	Maharashtra, Gujarat, Dadara & Nagar Haveli, Daman Diu	-	1	1
5	Punjab, Haryana & Rajasthan	-	1	1
6	Telangana & Andhra Pradesh	1	-	1
7	Andhra Pradesh & Odisha	1	-	1
8	Assam and Arunachal Pradesh	-	1	1
9	Karnataka & Kerala	2	-	2
10	Karnataka & Maharashtra	-	1	1
11	Kerala & Tamil Nadu	1	-	1
12	Manipur & Nagaland	1	-	1
13	Punjab / Haryana / Himachal Pradesh / Delhi / Uttarakhand / Uttar Pradesh / Jammu & Kashmir	1	-	1
14	Sikkim and West Bengal	1	-	1
15	Uttar Pradesh & Madhya Pradesh	1	-	1
16	Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh	1	-	1
	Total	13	4	17

Results: A total of 17 products get GI tags jointly out of which 13 are agricultural products and 4 are handicraft products.

6.3 Category-wise distribution of GI Tags

There are five categories of GI tags have been registered. These are Agricultural goods, Food Stuff, Handicraft products, Manufactured goods and Natural goods.

Table No.3: Statement showing category of goods for GI Tags

S.N.	Category of Goods	Total GI Tags	%
1	Agricultural	197	32.56
2	Food Stuff	45	7.44
3	Handicraft	342	56.53

S.N.	Category of Goods	Total GI Tags	%
4	Manufactured	18	2.98
5	Natural goods	3	0.50
	Total	605	100.00

Chart 2: Category wise distribution of GI tags

- Handicrafts (56.53%): The largest share of registered GIs comes from handicrafts - iconic items like Kanchipuram saris, Tanjore paintings, and Chola bronzes belong here.
- Agricultural goods (32.56%): A significant part encompasses produce such as mangoes, spices, and rice varieties.
- Food Stuff (7.44%): Notable foodstuffs with GI tags are Rasgulla (West Bengal & Odisha – both have separate GI tags), Mysore Pak (Karnataka), Bikaneri Bhujia (Rajasthan), Tirunelveli Halwa (Tamil Nadu), Srivilliputtur Palkova (Tamil Nadu) etc.
- Manufactured items including textiles (2.987%): Smaller shares. Textiles and manufactured goods (like perfumes, metal crafts) count for a smaller proportion.
- Natural goods (0.50%): this category occupies an even smaller percentage of GI registrations. Some notable items are Makrana Marble (Rajasthan), Mizo Chilli (Bird's Eye Chilli) Mizoram, Kashmir Saffron (Jammu & Kashmir), Marble Stone of Bhedaghat (Madhya Pradesh), Blue Pottery Clay (Rajasthan) Aluva Clay (Kerala) and so on.

6.3.1 Handicrafts

Handicrafts form the largest category among products with Geographical Indication (GI) tags in India. These are manually crafted traditional products that reflect the culture, skill, and heritage of a specific region. Their uniqueness is rooted in the local materials, artisanal techniques, and historical or cultural significance tied to a particular geography (Development Commissioner (Handicrafts), 2017).

Table 4: States/UTs wise distribution of Handicraft products

Sl. No.	States/UTs	No. of GI Tags
1	Jharkhand	1
2	Nagaland	1
3	Ladakh (UT)	2
4	Meghalaya	2
5	Pondicherry	2
6	Tripura	2
7	Manipur	3
8	Chhattisgarh	5
9	Mizoram	5
10	Himachal Pradesh	7
11	Bihar	9
12	Uttarakhand	9
13	Jammu & Kashmir	10
14	Arunachal Pradesh	11
15	Maharashtra	12
16	Madhya Pradesh	14
17	Andhra Pradesh	15
18	Kerala	15
19	Telangana	15
20	West Bengal	15
21	Odisha	16
22	Rajasthan	17
23	Karnataka	19
24	Assam	20
25	Gujarat	23
26	Tamil Nadu	35
27	Uttar Pradesh	53
	Grand Total	338

Chart 2: State wise distribution of GI tags for handicraft products

Results: A total of 338 handicraft products have been registered for GI tags out of 605 products during this study period. The above table shows that large number of GI tags found in Uttar Pradesh (53), Tamil Nadu (35), Gujrat (23) Assam (20) and so on. Almost same numbers (14 to 17) are found in case of Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Telangana, West Bengal, Odisha and Rajasthan. Only one or few numbers are found in Jharkhand, Nagaland, Ladakh (UT), Meghalaya, Pondicherry and in Tripura.

6.3.2 Agricultural Goods

Geographical Indication (GI) tags have been applied to a wide range of agricultural goods in India because of their distinctive characteristics related to geography, climate, soil, and traditional farming practices. These GI tags support local farmers and communities by preserving the identity, highlighting the distinctiveness, and raising the market value of the products.

Table 5: States/UTs wise distribution of Agricultural Goods

Sl. No.	States/UTs	No. of GI Tags by each State	Total
1	(i) Andhra Pradesh (ii) Rajasthan (iii) Sikkim (iv) Telangana (v) Tripura	1	5
2	(i) Chhattisgarh (ii) Himachal Pradesh (iii) Ladakh (UT) (iv) Mizoram	2	8
3	(i) Gujarat (ii) Manipur (iii) Meghalaya (iv) Nagaland	3	12
4	(i) Arunachal Pradesh (ii) Jammu & Kashmir (iii) Madhya Pradesh (iv) Odisha	4	16
5	Bihar	6	6
6	(i) Goa (ii) West Bengal	7	14
7	Assam	10	10
8	Uttar Pradesh	11	11
9	Tamil Nadu	14	14
10	Uttarakhand	15	15
11	Kerala	18	18
12	Karnataka	21	21
13	Maharashtra	34	34
Total			184

Results: A total of 184 GI tags are found for agricultural products in India. Highest number (34) of GI tags are found in Maharashtra, then Karnataka (21), Kerala (18). West Bengal and Goa have 7 GI tags separately on agricultural products. Only one or two GI tags are found in Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Telangana, Tripura, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Ladakh (UT) and in Mizoram.

6.3.3 Food Stuff

India has a wide variety of traditional food products that have received Geographical Indication (GI) tags, reflecting the rich culinary heritage of the country. GI tags for foodstuff help protect the identity and uniqueness of these regional products while supporting local economies and traditional farming or preparation methods.

Table 5: States/UTs wise distribution of Food Stuff

Sl.No.	States/UTs	No. of GI Tags
1	Arunachal Pradesh	1
2	Bihar	1
3	Karnataka	1
4	Rajasthan	1
5	Telangana	1
6	Tripura	1
7	Uttarakhand	1
8	Goa	2
9	Jammu & Kashmir	2
10	Kerala	2
11	Maharashtra	2
12	Andhra Pradesh	3
13	Madhya Pradesh	3
14	Odisha	5
15	West Bengal	5
16	Uttar Pradesh	6
17	Tamil Nadu	8
Grand Total		45

Results: A total of 45 GI tags are found for Food Stuff in different States/UTs in India. Tamil Nadu holds 8 tags which includes Srivilliputtur Palkova, Kovilpatti Kadalai Mittai, Palani Panchamirtham, Manapparai Murukku, Ooty Varkey, Udangudi Panangkarupatti, Salem Sago (Javvarisi) and Marthandam Honey. There are 6 tags in Uttar Pradesh. These are Hathras Hing, Muzaffarnagar Gur (Jaggery), Banaras Lal Peda, Jaunpur Imarti, Banaras Thandai, Banaras and Tirangi Barfi. West Bengal (for Bardhaman Sitabhog, Bardhaman Mihidana, Banglar Rasogolla, Sundarban Honey and Joynagar Moa) and Odisha (for Odisha Rasagola, Kendrapara Rasabali, Odisha Khajuri Guda, Dhenkanal Magji and Similipal Kai Chutney of Odisha) have 5 each GI tags.

6.3.4 Manufactured Goods

GI tags for manufactured goods help protect diverse artistic and cultural heritage of India. They ensure that authentic, traditional skills remain economically viable and globally recognized.

Table 6: States/UTs wise distribution of Manufactured Goods

Sl.No.	States/UTs	Manufactured
1	Assam	1
2	Goa	1

Sl.No.	States/UTs	Manufactured
3	Himachal Pradesh	1
4	Maharashtra	1
5	Meghalaya	1
6	Odisha	1
7	Uttarakhand	1
8	Tamil Nadu	2
9	Arunachal Pradesh	3
10	Karnataka	3
11	Uttar Pradesh	3
Total		18

Results: A total of 18 GI tags are found for manufactured goods in India. Some of these items are Kannauj Perfume (Logo), Meerut Scissors, Agra Leather Footwear for Uttar Pradesh; Mysore Agarbathi, Mysore Sandalwood Oil, Mysore Sandal Soap for Karnataka; Arunachal Pradesh Adi Apong, Arunachal Pradesh Dao (Sword), "Arunachal Pradesh Marua Apo (Marua Millet Beverage)" for Arunachal Pradesh; Coimbatore Wet Grinder, East India Leather for Tamil Nadu; Nainital Mombatti (Candle) for Uttarakhand; Ganjam Kewda Rooh for Odisha and so on.

6.3.5 Natural Goods

According to Geographical Indications of commodities (Registration and Protection) Act, 1999 in India, natural commodities are one of the four main categories that qualify for Geographical Indications (GI). Without much human involvement, these are items that naturally exist in a particular geographic location and have special characteristics brought about by the local environment, climate, or ecology.

There are three natural goods have been found in this study period for GI tags. These are Gujarat (for Ambaji White Marble), Rajasthan (Makrana Marble) and Uttar Pradesh (Chunar Balua Patthar).

7. Discussions

Due to a confluence of awareness, administrative, legal, and financial obstacles, the registration rate for Geographical Indications (GI) tags is comparatively low in India. Below is a summary of the main causes:

- Lack of Awareness: Limited Knowledge, No institutional support etc.
- Cumbersome registration process: Complex procedures, high costs, time-consuming process etc.
- Lack of legal and technical expertise: Preparing the application, defining the uniqueness of the product, drafting the statement of case
- Limited perceived benefits: Even after getting a GI tag, many products see little commercial gain because of poor marketing and branding, lack of access to national and international markets and no clear mechanism to enforce rights or prevent misuse.
- Other issues like weak post-registration support, fragmented producer communities, regional imbalance so on.

8. Conclusion

While providing local populations with economic opportunities, Geographical Indications (GIs) are essential to preserving rich cultural, agricultural, and artisanal legacy of India. By elevating and valuing regionally specific items, they act as a tool to preserve traditional knowledge and advance rural development. For GI tags to have a greater impact in India, there needs to be more grassroots education and awareness, streamlined processes, reasonably priced legal aid, proactive government support for branding, marketing, enforcement, and an emphasis on capacity-building of producer communities in India.

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